

How to talk on serious matters of complexity with models as agents – A speculative essay on artistic and design-based research

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Abstract

The essay will conceptualize models as cultural techniques, which catalyze fruitful discussions on serious matters of our commons, that is the cultural, natural and technological resources accessible to all members of a society. Models are called into action especially when these matters of concern transcend our intuitive understanding and reach a degree of complexity that goes beyond simple human reasoning. In such cases we need help from models. They show us and let us experience important aspects of the global, unforeseeable, emergent effects of our and our machine's day-to-day micro-behavior and usage of common resources and infrastructures. Models are mechanical machines, electronic analog computers, synthesizers, software simulations, games, ecological systems and much more.

This short and tentative essay is conceptualizing models as cultural techniques [1], agential[2] media and designed systems, which catalyze fruitful discussions on serious matters of our commons. With the term commons all the natural, technological and cultural resources accessible to all members of a community is meant. This is also relevant for artistic and design based research as it is argued in this essay. Models are called into action especially when these “matters of concern”[3] transcend our intuitive understanding and reach a degree of complexity[4] that goes beyond simple human reasoning. In such cases we need help from models. They show us, and let us experience important aspects of the unforeseeable, emergent, and sometimes global effects – both positive and negative – of our and our machine's day-to-day micro-behavior. Consisting of little actions they sum-up all together to affect our common resources and infrastructures.

Models manifest themselves as mechanical machines, analog computers, synthesizers, software simulations, games, animals, bacteria, ecological systems and much more. In general, they are crystallizations of scientific theory in agential matter, which we humans can see, feel and hear and as such they belong not only to the domain of science and technology, but also to art, design, architecture, dance and sound.

Models can be artistic or have an elaborated design. On their ways from techno-science to art galleries, design exhibitions, workshops and public interventions they go through a metamorphosis from ideally being functional to being diffractive, sometimes even dysfunctional. Following this thought, the essay addresses a yet to realize program of artistic and design-based research. This strategy intends to enable, catalyze and open-up fruitful discussions of the ongoing micro-design[5] of the different modes, rules and habits in the human and non-human mattering, enactment, organization and management of common resources, goods, knowledge and infrastructures..

Minor matters

During their endeavor to acquire new knowledge scientists and engineers usually apply established designs of instruments, tools, models and simulations. Often, they need to develop their own tools of experimentation, but unfortunately have rarely time to reflect and experiment upon their extended aesthetic, artistic and designerly aspects. While accuracy of content abstraction and technical functionality matter, these issues, although they are recognized, are of secondary importance. They are minor matters and do not appear on scientific research agendas. As the aesthetics of things, objects and processes are key competences of art and design, everything, which addresses the human sense-modalities, is a matter of our concern. Given the ongoing cost reduction in electronic tinkering, mechanical parts, computation power, robotics and rapid prototyping as well as the dawn of open soft- and hardware projects, researching serious matters of complexity with alternative models as agents in creative, but technologically-informed ways is at the edge of becoming an issue of application-oriented fundamental research done at art and design universities.

Practices of modeling are seen both in the field of the arts and in technoscience. Physical models for instance are used in both contexts. Nude models, model figures, clay models and sculptures indeed all sorts of assemblages of body and materials in artistic contexts are similar to scale models, model cars, globes, atom and molecule models massively used a long time ago in science and engineering. Nowadays they are only used for pedagogical purposes. Same applies to conceptual models, which are based on feedback circuits. The electronics used in analog computing, a long forgotten scientific field that proliferated between the 1920s and 1970s, is basically the same circuitry, which is later incorporated in audio and video synthesizers and used by many composers and artists since the 1960s, such as Nam June Paik (1932–2006), Steina and Woody Vasulka (*1940, *1937), Jack Burnham (*1931) and many more. Others such as John Cage (1912–1992) or Harald Haacke (1924–2004) experimented more conceptually with the idea of feedback.

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In technoscience the aim of modeling is “to represent an idea, concept, or situation, usually in a form that facilitates further analysis. The more malleable and flexible the modelling medium, the more powerful and experimental the modelling.”[6] With the dawn of digital computing in the 1980s scientific modeling was more and more done with simulations watched on computer screens. In parallel artists and designers started to use the computer for their creations. But while the creative still preferred diversity and used not only visual, but also sound-based forms of expression and always showed the hardware of their projects and works, scientists and engineers were more and more using only visual, screen-based media for their modeling. Understanding complexity by simulations applying agent-based modeling, for example, has been mostly done via eyes staring at some screen, interacting via keyboard and mouse, later by touch-screen.

The aesthetics of things, objects and processes are minor matters in technoscience. What counts is the content. Therefore the way simulations and modeling is done never changed substantially since the dawn of the pc. There are manifold reasons for this ongoing tendency towards visual and virtual abstraction[7]. One is certainly the above-mentioned malleability of digital media, and another the printability of computer graphics, but these can't get fully discussed here. Instead, I would like to give a brief general account on a speculative, yet to realize program of artistic and design-based research. A program that will liberate technoscientific models from their aesthetic constraints and boredom in order to make them more useful and understandable, still not simpler, but more complicated, affective, disrupting, disputable, more interfering, parasitic and troubling than before.

Common concerns

There are no consistent research programs without some theoretical backups, therefore some considerations: The legitimacy to do research in art and design shall not be questioned. It is pointless. We build on two assumptions. Firstly, artistic research and experimental design are techniques of emergence[8]. Secondly, research practices in science and engineering are similar to design processes[9]. Verification of both assumptions occurs only by concrete enactment and unfolding. Focusing on modeling complexity might be an interesting strategy within these conditions, since it affords a coupling to urgent global issues of governing the commons not only addressed to politicians and policy makers, scientists, engineers and critical thinkers such as sociologists, philosophers or historians, but, as I argue here, also to artists and designers.

Convincing examples of such urgent matters are cooperation dilemmas and issues among common pool resource's users. A common pool resource is a type of good consisting of natural, cultural or social resources like air, drink water, fishing grounds, pastures, forests, irrigation systems and generally all energy and nutrition resources, but also resources like literature, music, movies, all media products in general and open source software. According to our democratic ideals, these are all resources that are or should be held in common, not owned privately, since they affect all connected forces, parties, agents and humans, unquestioned of their geopolitically allocated influence factor. Disastrous effects of bad resource management and cooperation dilemmas such as traffic jams, over-fishing or even climate change often are results of complex interplay of all involved micro-forces

Resource sharing is not easy. The “Tragedy of the Commons” as formulated 1968 by Garrett J. Hardin (1915–2003) in an article in *Science* is one of the most famous social problems of common goods sharing. “Picture a pasture open to all. It is to be expected that each herdsman will try to keep as many cattle as possible on the commons. [...] Therein is the tragedy. Each man is locked into a system that compels him to increase his herd without limit – in a world that is limited.”[10] This will inevitably lead to an overexploitation and resource-depletion.

A little bit more than twenty years later Elinor Ostrom (1933–2012)[11] published ‘Governing the Commons’ (1990)[12] and therein referred to Hardin. Besides taking-up similar models such as the prisoner's dilemma game, she also took-up Mancur L. Olson's (1932–1998) ‘The Logic of Collective Action’ (1965), where he theorized that members of large groups do not act according to a common interest unless motivated by personal economic or social gain, while small groups can act on shared objectives. Personal gain leads to bad results, if the resource is limited. Obviously most resources are limited in some form.

Ostrom was more optimistic than her precursors and not only described many real-world cases, where sharing a common resource pool is working. By field research and referring to Game Theory, she famously formulated eight design principles for stable local common pool resource management[13]. Most importantly, operational rules of resource usage would need to get defined by the participants themselves, not from top-down, but bottom-up.

'Governing the Commons' was highly influential. In the last twenty-five years since 1990 models of common resource sharing were implemented in digital computer simulations and concepts from cybernetics[14], system dynamics[15], chaos theory[16] and even cellular automata theory have informed this still evolving field of research[17]. Already Ostrom herself not only referred to W. Ross Ashby's (1903–1972) 'An Introduction to Cybernetics', but also both Thomas Schelling's (*1921) 'Micromotives and Macrobehavior' and Ilya Prigogine's (1917–2003) 'Time, Structure and Fluctuations'[18]. Both are discourse-founding Nobel Prize-lectures (1978, 1977) for establishing research in emergent, counter-intuitive group behavior, nonlinear dynamics, self-organization and research on complex systems.

Modeling the complexity of micro-actions within the field of the commons is promising, not only because of these and other connections, which allow innovative links to alternative modes of modeling beyond digital simulations, such as analog computing, feedback circuitry and hybrid models. More recent research on the commons combined with computer gaming is equally promising. As of 2015, after the rise of serious gaming[19], tragedy of commons games are playable online. Still the steps to a recursive application back to common pool resource's users in order to inform them are rare, while the importance of self-organization and self-governance has already been formulated[20]. A conventional design task would then be to facilitate and enable such processes of self-organization by improving aspects of visual communication, product or interaction design. Victor Papanek (1923–1998) has been from the 1970s on one of the first to combine ecological thinking with product design. More recent emerging research fields are participatory design, design in the context of citizen science, eco-design, sustainability and transformative design. And indeed, such projects hopefully provoke interest from institutions such as the 'Centre for Policy Modelling' in Manchester[21]. A slightly more radical approach would claim that playing a prisoner's dilemma or a tragedy of commons game is not enough, but making, programming and designing such a game involves much more learning and is therefore much more effective.

Diffraction modeling

Designerly work and aesthetic experimentation with the communicative affordances models within fields such as the commons are offering unfolds firstly, via contact with policy makers and managers working in organizations acting in these fields, but secondly also via linking more directly with the involved actors, users and workers.

The experience of complex matters via artist and design based sense making with models and interaction is surely insightful. An emphasis on enabling not just a reflective, but a *diffraction* understanding[22] about common pool resources might prove to create stronger impacts. This is the speculation this short essay builds upon.

According to Karen Barad (*1956) and Donna Haraway (*1944) diffraction, in comparison to reflection, which is the common term used in conjunction with critical inquiry or critical thinking, is not merely about mirroring without influence, but about positive interfering, blurring, bending and transforming with the content under study[23]. It is sort of a spurious *différance*[24] or a smeary differentiation. When you drop two stones in a pond they generate ripples, interferences and interweavings on the water surface. Similarly fields as diverse as the arts and technoscience could positively interfere with each other, still maintaining their specificity and characteristics. A diffraction inquiry is both transforming and bending its subject in order to create a range of alternative approaches for its study, but also tries to keep high-fidelity concerning its sources.

Diffraction modeling means consequently to design communication between the matter to understand, the model and its user in a highly flexible, if not an agential manner. Agential is a term I borrowed again from Barad. Quantum physics showed us that "theoretical concepts are defined by the circumstance required for their measurement." [25] This means, "that there is no unambiguous way to differentiate between the 'object' and the 'agencies of observation.'" [26] Not only is the user (inter)acting with the model. The model is acting back and becomes an agent. Model, user and creator are all, as agents, coupled to each other like in a *ménage à trois*. As Henri Poincaré (1854–1912) showed, three interacting bodies generate nonlinear dynamics. [27] A minor change in the condition of one of those three is agential upon the remaining two. Furthermore, like in quantum physics, where a particle can become a wave and vice versa, [28] diffraction modeling is never static. Ideally, it is unfailingly experimental, slippery, strange and peculiar, not sticking to one version of modeling, but constantly re-searching new forms of representation, aesthetization and sense making. It therefore demands a lot of effort.

To be more concrete concerning different techniques of modeling, a first step would be to broaden the current aesthetic qualities of simulation and modeling by transgressing again to physical space and real-world processes – as it was done in the past with physical models, electrical equivalents (analog computing) and mechanical sorts of models.

Furthermore, by combining digital computation with electronics and real-world actuators such as motors, electromagnets, hydraulic, optical or acoustic systems and more advanced sorts of transducers – simply spoken by combining hardware with software or by carrying out physical computing – positive diffractions of current modeling and simulation practices could emerge. Neighboring fields such as interface/interaction design and research on the so-called Internet of Things at institutions such as the MIT Media Lab, Royal College of Art, ETH Zurich and many more are offering thousands of starting points to unfold diffractive modeling.

It was not by accident that for a long time interactive modeling was regarded as the domain of analog computing, while information processing and calculation as the competence of digital computation.[29] Analog systems operate in real-time, there is no symbolical translation of the matter in action. No data involved. That was its specificity, but the acceleration of digital processing made it redundant. Historical ignorance is obviously no option. Digital simulation shall thus not get abandoned, but extended with analog computing: Agent-based modelling not only as virtual simulation, but more as some sort of tangible real-world happening, not fully out of, but a little bit under control.

The history of analog computing affords a whole ecosystem of strange apparatuses, peculiar assemblages and unheard-of models. Soap bubbles were used in aerospace engineering for obtaining mathematical solutions of the so-called Laplace equation. Their surface was an analogon for mathematical principles.[30] Hydraulic flow systems were used to model the national economy of the UK.[31] Electrolytic tanks were used broadly for oil reservoir modeling[32] or so called rotating dishpan models for chaotic fluid dynamics.[33] Could such strange apparatuses become diffractive models for experiencing and understanding current matters of concerns? In the early 1960s British cybernetician Stafford Beer (1926–2002), was experimenting with organisms such as leeches in an artificial pond, which would model a whole economy. He did not succeed, but in a recent scientific field called unconventional computing leeches were used as models of human fleeing behavior inside buildings.[34]

Diffractive modeling is not meant to become fully useful in its straightforward meaning. It is not about utilizing creativity in order to solve global issues. It is more about addressing them by interactive involvement via modeling and experiences, which provoke new alternatives of established practices. Diffractive practices need to stay vague and experimental, in order to enable new modes of coupling. At the same time it is important to keep it down to earth and establish a high-fidelity with the sources of the interference. How to talk on serious matters of complexity with models as agents is not an answer, but a question, which should indeed be the main driving source of such a difficult endeavor.

References

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- [3]Bruno Latour, “Why Has Critique Run out of Steam? From Matters of Fact to Matters of Concern,” *Critical Inquiry* 30, no. 2 (Jan 1, 2004): 231f..
- [4]I define complexity as a phenomenon linked to a system, network, collection or assemblage with many parts where those parts interact with each other in multiple ways, so that they generate effects that are unforeseen, not in order (predictable), nor totally random, but in-between these states. See Melanie Mitchell, *Complexity. A Guided Tour* (Oxford/New York: Oxford University Press, 2009).
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- [7] Early work by Bruno Latour are pertinent for this question, see Bruno Latour, “Visualisation and Cognition: Thinking with Eyes and Hands,” *Knowledge and Society Studies in the Sociology of Culture Past and Present* 6 (1986): 1–40; Bruno Latour and Steve Woolgar, *Laboratory Life: The Construction of Scientific Facts* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1986).
- [8]„Experimental practice embodies technique toward catalyzing an event of emergence whose exact lineament cannot be foreseen. [...] Technique is therefore processual: it reinvents itself in the evolution of a practice. [...] This idea of research-creation as embodying techniques of emergence takes it seriously that a creative art or design practice launches concepts in-the-making.“ from Erin Manning, Brian Massumi: *Thought in the Act: Passages in the Ecology of Experience*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2014, 89.
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[22] Thanks to my friend and current work colleague Jamie C. Allen for hinting me to this important vein of post-feminist materialist theory.

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[29] Care, *Technology for Modelling*, 71.

[30] *Ibid.*, 143.

[31] *Ibid.*, 5.

[32] *Ibid.*, 123.

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